

Voltammetric study of lipoxygenase bio-electrode on fatty acids components of palm oil

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Abstract : This work addresses the electrooxidation of fatty acids components of palm oil namely (palmitic acid, linolic acid, linolinic acid, myristic acid, and stearic acid) on lipoxygenase electrodes applying cyclic voltammetry. The effect of different concentration of these fatty acids were investigated using a conventional three-electrode cell. The results show irreversible or quasi-reversible signals with oxidation peak potentials values between 0.15 and 0.62 V and reduction potentials values between -0.125 and 0.52 V to all fatty acids evaluated. The CVs recorded in these fatty acids show some diversity with differences in the peak current values of the redox process. High current densities were obtained at various substrate concentrations depending on the type of fatty acid used. All of these fatty acids have exhibited to some degree of electrocatalytic activity with lipoxygenase bio-electrode. But only linolic acid has displayed relatively superior performances.

Keywords : Electrooxidation, lipoxygenase, fatty acids, palm oil.

Introduction

Lipoxygenases LOXs (linoleate : oxygen oxidoreductase, EC1.13.11.12) are mononuclear non-heme iron enzymes, originate in both plants and animals¹, that catalyze the regio and stereospecific dioxygenation of *cis,cis*-1,4-pentadiene containing fatty acids e.g. linoleic acid, α -linolenic acid, or arachidonic acid to alkyl hydroperoxides^{2,3}. Numerous kinetics studies have been carried out using plant lipoxygenase due to their relatively high stability and availability and their kinetically tractable compared to mammalian lipoxygenase⁴. Therefore, the majority of studies of lipoxygenase kinetics and mechanism have been carried out using soy bean lipoxygenase⁵.

The first step of lipoxygenase (LOX) reaction is the elimination of a hydrogen atom from a methylene unit between double bonds in substrate fatty acids⁶. The stabilization of the resulting carbon radical is approached from the electron delocalization through the double bonds. After that, the introduction of a molecular oxygen to the carbon atom at +2 or -2 position from the original radical carbon is take place, then a peroxy radical and a conjugated *trans, cis*-diene chromophore are produced⁷. Then the peroxy radical is hydrogenated to produce a hydroperoxide. The preliminary hydrogen elimination and the following oxygen adding take place in opposite sides related

to the plane produced by the 1Z,4Z-pentadiene unit⁸.

Mammalian LOXs are classified according to their positional specificity of arachidonic oxygenation into 5-, 8-, 12- and 15-LOXs⁹. While in cases of plant LOXs, the common substrates are C18-polyunsaturated fatty acids (linoleic and α -linolenic acids) and classified into 9-LOXs, 13-LOXs, or 9/13-LOXs¹⁰.

The development of lipoxygenase bioanodes which utilized in a soy bean oil biofuel cell has been reported. Lipoxygenase is proved to be capable of oxidizing saturated as well as unsaturated fatty acids components of soy bean oil¹¹. We previously reported a preliminary electrochemical study of lipoxygenase bioelectrode in the oxidation of hydrolyzed cooking palm oil¹². The aim of the present study is to present knowledge on cyclic voltammetric behavior of lipoxygenase bioelectrode in the oxidation of fatty acids components of palm oil (palmitic acid, linolic acid, linolinic acid, myristic acid, and stearic acid) at different concentrations.

Results and discussion

Effect of different concentration of linolic acid :

The non-heme iron that is present in lipoxygenase enzyme is found in two oxidation states, Fe^{II} and Fe^{III}. This condition mediates the electron transfer reactions for the

formation of lipid peroxide¹³. The catalysis appears to involve redox cycling of the iron atom. The Fe^{II} species obtained in the hydrogen abstraction step transfers an electron to the peroxy radical intermediate, along with proton transfer, to complete the catalyzed reaction and regenerate the Fe^{III} form for further catalytic cycles. The time course for the catalyzed reaction has a distinctively auto-catalytic appearance¹⁴.

In this work linolic acid was used as substrate by lipoxygenase enzyme immobilized in modified Nafion membrane on the carbon electrode. The effect of different concentrations of linolic acid was studied over the range of 2–6 g on the response of lipoxygenase-modified carbon electrode (Fig. 1). The voltammogram is scanned between –0.5 V and 1 V (vs Ag/AgCl) at a scan rate of 100 mV s⁻¹. Fig. 1a shows two oxidation peaks at 0.150 V and 0.625 V respectively, the weak reduction peak was observed at the potential of 0.3 V. As the concentration of linolic acid is increase the irreversibility was confirmed by the absence of cathodic peak in voltammogram (Fig. 1b). Furthermore, the two oxidation peaks became one broad peak along with disappearance of cathodic peak was observed with the excessive increase in the linolic acid concentrations. Similar electrochemical behavior has been already observed in Figs. 1d and e. This behavior may be due to a decreased activity of the electrode at high linolic acid concentrations, probably due to competition for active sites on the electrode surface.

Effect of different concentration of olic acid :

The effect of different concentrations of olic acid on the response of lipoxygenase-modified carbon electrode has been studied (Fig. 2). As shown in Fig. 2a, a broad peak was observed in system when the olic acid concentration is 2 g. While in (Fig. 2b) and after the addition of 3 g of olic acid two I_{pa} are observed at 0.150 V and 0.625 V respectively. With the successive addition of olic acid (Figs. 2c, d and e) the anodic peak showed hardly catalytic current, again the two oxidation peaks became one broad peak along with slight diminishment in the I_{pa} upon the augmentation of olic acid concentration.

Effect of different concentration of palmitic acid :

Fig. 3 showed the cyclic voltammograms of palmitic acid solutions at the bare lipoxygenase electrode. A broad anodic peak appeared at 0.25 V on the bare electrode

(Fig. 3a). The lipoxygenase electrode exhibited effective electrocatalysis toward palmitic acid concentration increase, resulting in the peak current increase (Figs. 3b and c). The reduction peak current is appeared to some extent at 0.45 V. Meanwhile, the oxidation peak current was also somewhat suppressed, suggesting that the well defined quasi-reversible electrochemical redox occurring in lipoxygenase electrode was varied in some degree.

Effect of different concentration of mystric acid :

The voltammetric behavior of Mystric acid is shown in Figs. 4a and b two main oxidation peaks appear during the positive potentials at 0.15 and 0.52 V, respectively. The first peak at the low potential region is may often attributed to the dehydrogenation of mystric acid on the electrode surface, producing a layer of adsorbed mystric acid intermediates on the electrode surface. These intermediate species were then oxidized at a higher potential, resulting in the second peaks. The small peak in the lower part are due to the reduction of a secondary unstable species.

On the other hand, upon the addition of 4 g mystric acid to the supporting electrolyte, the anodic current starts to increase at 0.15 V, due to the oxidation of mystric acid. In this case, the reduction current increases with the concentration of mystric acid added. This is due to the formation of mystric acid hydroperoxide via the lipoxgenase reaction as depicted in Section 3.1. Beyond 4 g of mystric acid weight the current density is significantly decreased (Figs. 4d and e). This might be due to that the lipoxygenase reaction is affected by mystric acid implicates groups in the vicinity of the active sites of lipoxygenase.

Effect of different concentration of stearic acid :

The cyclic voltammogram of 2 g of stearic acid (Fig. 5a) indicates two redox couples; the first couples with cathodic peak potential (E_{pc} –0.125 V) and anodic peak potential (E_{pa} 0.25 V) and the second couples with (E_{pc} 0.525 V) and (E_{pa} 0.425 V). Upon the addition of 3 g of stearic acid (Fig. 5b) a significant augmentation in the first anodic peak was observed along with diminishment in the other peaks. However, when the stearic acid concentration exceeded more than 3 g I_{pa} starts to decrease (Figs. 5c, d and e).

The feasibility of the voltammetric detection of the

Fig. 1. The cyclic voltammogram of lipoxygenase-modified carbon electrode at different concentration of linolic acid, (a) 2 g, (b) 3 g, (c) 4 g, (d) 5 g and (e) 6 g, scan rate 100 mV s^{-1} .

interaction of these substrates with this enzyme implies the following assessments (a) each substrate undergoes redox reactions, at the working electrode which give rise to either quasi-reversible or irreversible electrodic processes within a suitable potential window. This correlates with the fact that, lipoxygenase enzyme has the capability to oxidize all fatty acids used in this study both saturated and unsaturated type. (b) The resulting voltammograms

of all fatty acids used generate almost irreversible or quasi-reversible signals with oxidation peak potentials values between 0.15 and 0.62 V and reduction potentials values between -0.125 and 0.52 V .

On the basis of the relationship between the type of fatty acids and redox peak currents, we can notice that the highest current are produced by the unsaturated fatty ac-

Fig. 2. The cyclic voltammogram of lipoxygenase-modified carbon electrode at different concentration of olic acid, (a) 2 g, (b) 3 g, (c) 4 g, (d) 5 g and (e) 6 g, scan rate 100 mV s^{-1} .

ids, the highest current produced by linolenic acid which is the most unstable fatty acid in palm oil due to the presence of three double bonds¹⁵ is about 1.5 mA, while in case of oleic acid, with only one double bond in its structure, was more stable, which is indicated by the statistically significantly high current about 2.5 mA. In case of saturated fatty acids it was noted the response of palmitic acid (0.5 mA), stearic acid (0.5 mA) and myristic acid (0.43 mA) was found to be the smallest.

Materials and methods :

Chemicals :

Lipoxygenase-1 (type I-B) (SLO) (linoleate/oxygen oxidoreductase; EC1.13.11.12) from soybean, palmitic acid, linolic acid, linolenic acid, myristic acid and stearic acid were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Japan). Other chemicals were of analytical grade and purchased from various sources. All solutions were freshly prepared using ultrapure water (18.6 M cm) from Milli-Q plus of Millipore Corp. (USA).

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Fig. 3. The cyclic voltammogram of lipoxygenase-modified carbon electrode at different concentration of palmitic acid, (a) 2 g, (b) 3 g, (c) 4 g, (d) 5 g and (e) 6 g, scan rate 100 mV s^{-1} .

Instrumentation :

Voltammetric experiments were carried out with electrochemical workstation Epsilon 2 of Bioanalytical System (BAS) (USA). A three electrode system was employed, with a platinum wire as counter electrode and pseudo Ag/AgCl as the reference electrode. Voltammetric responses of 10 mL fatty acids solutions in potassium phosphate buffer (pH 7) were recorded at an applied potential of -500 to 1000 mV (vs Ag/AgCl). The pH of solution was obtained using pH/ISE meter 720A from Orion (USA).

Voltammetry study :

1 cm^2 of carbon cloth B-1 (Clean Fuel Cell Energy

LLC, USA). Then, it was allowed to dry prior to modification. The lipoxygenase enzyme solution was prepared by adding 2 mg of enzyme to 5 mL of phosphate buffer (pH 7). Casting solutions for making the mixture-cast membranes of Nafion and quaternary ammonium bromides were prepared as described elsewhere¹⁶. Enzyme and Nafion casting solutions, with a ratio of 1 : 1 were vortexed prior to coating on the electrode. The mixture was pipetted on the surface of electrode and allowed to dry in a low humidity environment before any electrical measurement was made.

Preparation of fatty acids solutions :

The fatty acids solutions were prepared by mixing dif-

Fig. 4. The cyclic voltammogram of lipoxigenase-modified carbon electrode at different concentration of myristic acid, (a) 2 g, (b) 3 g, (c) 4 g, (d) 5 g and (e) 6 g, scan rate 100 mV s^{-1} .

ferent concentrations (2, 3, 4, 5, 6) g and 10 ml phosphate buffer ($0.044 \text{ M KH}_2\text{PO}_4$, 0.044 M NaOH and 0.15 M NaCl) (pH 7).

Conclusion

In this work the oxidation of fatty acids components of palm oil at different concentrations was studied using lipoxigenase immobilized in ammonium modified Nafion

membrane on carbon electrode. Cyclic voltammetry was the main technique used to characterize the behavior of these fatty acids. Lipoxigenase enzyme exhibits the potential to oxidize fatty acids both saturated and unsaturated sort producing a well-shaped almost reversible or quasi-reversible signals the highest current are produced by the unsaturated fatty acids, the performance of saturated fatty acids nearly analogous and lower than unsaturated fatty acids.

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Fig. 5. The cyclic voltammogram of lipoxygenase-modified carbon electrode at different concentration of stearic acid, (a) 2 g, (b) 3 g, (c) 4 g, (d) 5 g and (e) 6 g, scan rate 100 mV s^{-1} .

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